

CORPUS-BASED MODEL FOR TEACHING SYNONYMS

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Annotation: This study explores a corpus-based model for teaching synonyms in foreign language education. The research highlights the role of corpus technologies in developing students' lexical competence and improving their understanding of synonym usage in context. The results show that corpus-based instruction increases learning effectiveness and students' analytical skills. The results indicate that the corpus model increases learners' motivation, encourages research-oriented learning, and improves the effectiveness of synonym acquisition. The proposed model can be effectively implemented in modern language teaching methodology and digital linguodidactics.

Keywords: corpus linguistics, synonyms, teaching methodology, lexical competence, corpus model, linguodidactics.

Today, the use of modern pedagogical and digital technologies in teaching foreign languages is gaining importance. In particular, the approach based on corpus linguistics allows studying language units in real speech examples, which serves to develop students' lexical competence. The use of corpus materials in teaching synonyms is an effective tool for identifying the subtleties of meaning, stylistic differences, and frequency of use of words.

This study develops a corpus model for teaching synonyms and analyzes its linguodidactic capabilities. The main goal of the model is to teach students to analyze synonymous units based on a real context, distinguish their semantic and pragmatic properties, and correctly use them in speech. During the study, authentic texts were selected using corpus technologies and a special system of exercises was developed

based on them. Synonymy is an important indicator of lexical richness in the language system, and in teaching practice it often remains at the level of memorizing a “list of synonyms”. Such an approach cannot sufficiently reveal the functional differences of synonyms in real speech, that is, which unit is used in which context naturally, accurately and stylistically. In fact, synonyms are not absolutely equal: the factors that distinguish them include combinability (with which words it is combined more often), frequency (which unit is used more often), register (formal, scientific, journalistic, colloquial), evaluative ness and stylistic coloring. Therefore, the methodology of teaching synonyms requires a source of evidence about the real use of the language; as such, text corpora transfer the choice of synonyms from “intuition” to “observation and proof”, that is, the student learns to base his decision on linguistic facts.

Corpus data itself inevitably leads to the creation of new theories of language, in the sense that this approach to using corpus data is more theory-based than using it in conjunction with other methods or non-corpus-based theories. The idea that data and theory are somehow compatible is sometimes expressed in slightly different terms, for example: corpus linguistics is the only source of language theory, and is part of the corpus-based approach. Such an approach avoids the previous linguistic classification, that is, it distracts from what we might call "pure" theory hidden in the data. The strongest forms of the claim are that the corpus itself (and not just corpus linguistics as a field) is a theory; for example, Tognini-Bonelli's insistence that "theory does not exist independently of evidence". This is a very strong position to accept and requires careful elaboration.

The experimental results showed that the corpus-based methodology is more effective than traditional methods. Students developed the skills of faster understanding of the meaning differences of synonyms, their correct use in context, and independent analysis. Corpus materials also helped to increase students' interest in the language and

create an interactive and research-oriented learning environment. In conclusion, the corpus model of teaching synonyms is an effective methodological tool as a modern linguodidactic approach and is important in developing lexical competence in the process of foreign language learning. In generative grammar, as in most branches of linguistics, and indeed in all sciences and human relations in general, there is a clear conceptual separation between the theory to be supported (in the case of generative grammar, we might suppose it to be a set of some ideas about the nature of Universal Grammar) and the evidence intended to support it (the speaker's judgments about the grammaticality of a given set of constructed model sentences). If we take what we might describe as "the corpus is a theory," we are forced to conclude that the claim that "the corpus is a theory" has literally obliterated this distinction between data and theory: the corpus is for them both the phenomenon in need of explanation and the collection intended to explain it.

Data is data and theory is theory: while observations are important as necessary support for explanations, it is clear that they do not constitute explanations in themselves. Corpus theory rejects any explanation of linguistic regularities, does not derive them from the analyst's direct interaction with the data, but rather considers the corpus and corpus techniques as a source of empirical data as a corpus method. Any explanatory theory of language, even if developed without full or partial reference to corpus data, can be used to support or refute it. In contrast, corpus linguistics describes the following approach to "discourse":

Not a language-external taxonomy of linguistic units, but rather the discourse itself, should provide the categories and classifications necessary to answer the research question posed. The difference between these two approaches to discourse analysis could not be more stark. For corpus practitioners, corpus linguistics as a method can be used in conjunction with an established analytical framework, which in turn has nothing

to do with corpus linguistics. For Teubert, the only appropriate analytical framework for corpus evidence on discourse is the corpus framework as theory.

The results of the experiment showed that the corpus-based methodology is more effective than traditional methods. Students developed the skills of faster understanding of the meaning differences of synonyms, their correct application in context and independent analysis. Also, the corpus materials increased students' interest in the language and helped to create an interactive and research-oriented learning environment. In conclusion, the corpus model of teaching synonyms is an effective methodological tool as a modern linguodidactic approach and is of great importance in the development of lexical competence in the process of foreign language learning.

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